

Freezing of water as a propagation mechanism in a Thermal Snail

A solution to the IPT-problem "Thermal Snail"

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Abstract

Extracting energy from variations in atmospheric temperature has previously been studied in literature with promising results. These energy extractions can be illustrated by building an autonomous device that moves due to daily temperature fluctuations. This study used the mechanism of a wax engine, replacing the wax with freezing water, together with a novel design for a crankshaft to convert the volume expansion due to freezing into torque. The freezing water was shown to generate significant torque, and through a gearbox, many revolutions of an axle. This mechanism was attached to wheels, effectively forming a car with a water based cylinder as engine. A prototype of this mechanism was build with 4 mL of water in a syringe driving a car drivetrain. Every cycle of the water freezing and melting resulted in a propagation of 2.1 cm and the mechanism returned to its initial state. A simple theoretical model for the freezing and melting time was constructed. Historical temperature data from 1990 – 2020 at three sites in Sweden, by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, was used as input to the model and estimated that the device would move (90.7 ± 23.3) cm per year. The materials the prototype was constructed with were not capable of handling the forces of decreased gear ratios, but this could be mitigated by a more thorough manufacturing of the entire device and increase the propagation in a single cycle significantly. The freezing time could also be improved in several ways, although this is not expected to improve the distance traveled by more than a factor of 3.

Keywords: Thermal expansion, wax motor, drivetrain, crankshaft

1 Introduction

This section presents weather conditions in Sweden and the scope of this report.

1.1 Problem statement

International Physics Tournament (IPT) is an international competition in experimental physics where students from around the world try to solve open ended physics question within different disciplines of physics. The following problem from the 2024 edition forms the basis of this report,

Make an autonomous device that makes use of thermal expansion to move due to daily temperature fluctuations. Your device should work in the shade and is not allowed to include any electronics or piezoelectric elements for transduction. Furthermore, you are not allowed to exploit any temperature difference between the device and the surface it is on. Maximize its speed for a fixed maximum linear dimension of 10 cm and your outdoor weather conditions (or equivalent laboratory conditions if the outside weather is not suited to the experiment). [1]

This is interpreted as the following tasks

1. Investigate weather conditions in Sweden
2. Build a engine that generates force using thermal expansion
3. Build a propulsion mechanism centered around the engine output
4. Approximate the maximal performance of the device based on weather data

1.2 Weather conditions in Sweden

Data from the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute [2] was used to investigate Swedish weather conditions. The data was hourly temperature between 1990 and 2020 recorded 2 m above the ground. Three stations were investigated: Göteborg A, Krångede A and Nikkaloukta A¹ as shown in figure 1. The data is presented as box plots for each station in figure 2. The difference between the maximum and minimal temperature in a given day was calculated and plotted in a histogram in figure 3.

¹These stations were chosen because of geographic spread and proximity to where the author have spent a significant amount of time.

Figure 1: Locations of weather stations used as a reference for determining suitable temperature ranges. From south to north, Göteborg A at latitude 57.72°, Krångede A at latitude 63.15° and Nikkaluokta A at latitude 67.85° [2].

Figure 2: Temperature data at three stations from 1990 until 2020 from SMHI [2]. Red line is average value and only most extreme fliers are shown.

Figure 3: Distribution of daily temperature differences, defined as the maximum temperature minus the minimum temperature in a given day. Integral of the entire curve is 1.

The distribution of absolute temperatures and daily ranges of temperatures vary significantly with seasons, e.g. days with a greater temperature spread typically occur during early spring and temperatures below 0°C are not seen during summer. This will not be considered in this analysis, instead the aim will be to utilize weather phenomena such that the yearly average is as optimal as possible and the final design will be tested against the entire datasets. The data in figures 2 and 3 will be used to investigate the feasibility of expansion mechanisms from literature in Swedish climate in section 2.1.

2 Theoretical justifications and derivations

This section motivates the choice of "thermal engine" and how it would be integrated into a larger propulsion mechanism.

2.1 Mechanism of thermal expansion

This section gives an overview of methods of thermal expansion available in literature and discusses their applicability for the problem statement.

2.1.1 Linear thermal expansion

Thermal heat expansion can be described with the thermal expansion coefficient α_V . The volumetric heat expansion for an isotropic material is given by $\Delta V/V = \alpha_V \Delta T$ [3]. From figure 3 it is clear that temperature differences greater than 20°C are rare. At that temperature and using methanol, whose expansion coefficient is large compared to other liquids, $\alpha_V \approx 0.0015 \text{ K}^{-1}$ [4] would yield an approximate expansion of 3%. The solid stearic acid, which expands more than most other solids, has $\alpha_V \approx 0.0008 \text{ K}^{-1}$ [5] and would expand less than 2%. An ideal gas would expand as the ratio between the temperatures measured in Kelvin, which for an temperature difference from -10°C to 10°C would expand approximately 8%.

A method to increase the thermal displacement from solids is to use so called bimetals. They consist of two metals with different thermal expansion coefficients welded together. When the temperature changes the metal bends and results in a comparatively large displacement. Using a typical bimetal that is one hundred times longer than thick² would only result in a perpendicular displacement of 3% of the length [7].

2.1.2 Phase transitions

Xiao, Naclerio and Hawkes (2019) [8] investigated a liquid/gas transition to harness energy from fluctuation in atmospheric temperature. Their device was tuned to work in suitable temperatures by adjusting the pressure of the working gas, shifting the temperature for the corresponding vapor pressure. The final design was able to perform a maximum isobaric work of 2.3 J resulting in a energy density of 0.038 J mL^{-1} . Xiao et al. was able to fit the design in a simple car like design and make it move 10 m during a thermodynamic cycle. The design has several limiting factors in relation to the problem formulation posed in this study. Optimizing the design for Swedish temperature ranges would necessarily require a lower boiling point, as illustrated by figure 2, which using the equation for work formulated by Xiao et al. would decrease the work both by lowering operating temperature and lowering the pressure to decrease the boiling point. Further, the mechanical design does not perform any work during the cooling process, only when heating the liquid. Lastly, the device size far exceeds the limitations of this study and in relation to the

²The bending force from a thin bimetal is low which further complicates the usage. An excellent discussion on the limitations of bimetals was given by Team Germany at the International Physicists' Tournament 2024 Grand Finale [6].

work performed, the gas expansion requires a large volume. Thus, shrinking the volume would significantly reduce the work that the system is able to perform.

A wax motor is a readily available component that uses a solid liquid transition of wax to create a large force during its 5%–20% expansion [9, 10]. Waxes are available with various melting points, but are typically greater than 24°C, which would not work effectively in the Swedish climate³ [11, 12]. When water freezes it expands approximately 9% [13] at a temperature much more suitable for Swedish climate. This insight forms the basis of the "Thermal Snail" being constructed in this report.

2.2 Water isobaric heat capacity and expansion

Water is able to perform significant amounts of work when freezing, as illustrated by the recurring problem in Sweden with bursting pipes when ice freezes [14]. This is because when water freezes in a confined area the expansion will increase the pressure until it exceed what the pipe can handle. For moderate increases in pressure the freezing temperature does not change, which would be the case for the liquid-gas transition. A pressure of 10 MPa would change the freezing point to approximately -1°C although the expansion would increase to 14% [15, 16]. That pressure would require a steel pipe with 0.9 mm steel tube thickness and inner radius less than 16 mm [17]. However, a pressure of 10 MPa exceed what will be used in this study by several orders of magnitude. This implies that if water was used as the working fluid in a wax motor, which effectively confines the water except in one direction where it is free to expand, a significant resistive force can be against the direction of expansion. This would increase the pressure of the water inside, but as shown, the pressure can be significantly increased and the device with behave essentially the same as without the increase pressure.

2.3 Simplified model

The discussion in section 2.2 motivates why the thermal properties of water can be assumed to be constant at different pressures for the purposes of this study. Further, assuming that the heat transfer into the liquid, which in this case is water, follows Newtons law of cooling, during the cooling as well as freezing/melting process the following energy balance is proposed:

$$\dot{Q} = A_{\text{radiating}} h_{\text{coefficient}} \Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}$$

$$E_{T_{\text{low}} \rightarrow T_{\text{high}}} = d_{\text{expansion}} F_{\text{load}} + m_{\text{water}} \times \left(\int_{T_{\text{low}}}^{T_{\text{formation}}} C_P dT + h_{\text{latent}} + \int_{T_{\text{formation}}}^{T_{\text{high}}} C_P dT \right), \quad (1)$$

where \dot{Q} is the thermal energy entering the system per unit time, $A_{\text{radiating}}$ is the area exposed to the surroundings, $h_{\text{coefficient}}$ is the heat transfer coefficient between the surroundings and the water, $\Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}$ is temperature difference between the water and surrounding at any given moment, $E_{T_{\text{low}} \rightarrow T_{\text{high}}}$ is the energy required to change the water temperature from the temperature T_{low} to T_{high} including a phase transition with latent heat h_{latent} . The work performed by the system is the load force F_{load} over the maximal expansion distance $d_{\text{expansion}}$. $T_{\text{formation}}$ is the melting point of water and the total water mass, meaning solid and liquid, is denoted by m_{water} . The isobaric heat capacity is C_P and varies with temperature, it is however assumed to be constant for ice and water respectively in the considered temperature ranges.

When optimizing such a system, the water pressure p_{water} is approximated by,

$$p_{\text{water}} = F_{\text{load}} / A_{\text{piston}} \quad (2)$$

where A_{piston} is the area of the piston head that is moved by the expansion. This indicates whether the freezing properties have changed significantly and how strong the walls that confine the water has to be.

³Although I'm currently on an exchange in Brazil where it would be feasible, although practice it is hard to procure any wax with a melting point lower than 35°C [11].

The expansion state of the system in a given moment is approximated by the ratio of mass of water as ice m_{ice} to the total mass of water in all states m_{water} . The expression for the expansion d at a given time t is given by $d(t) = d_{\text{expansion}} r_{\text{ice/water}}$, where the ice to total mass ratio is defined by $r_{\text{ice/water}} = m_{\text{ice}}/m_{\text{water}}$. When T_{low} and T_{high} are close to each other, which is what is typical in a given day as seen in figure 3, the energy required to change the temperature of the water is small and can be neglected. If the mechanical work is also neglected, the equation (1) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{dr_{\text{ice/water}}}{dt} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } r_{\text{ice/water}} = 1 \text{ and } \Delta T_{\text{surrounding}} \leq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } r_{\text{ice/water}} = 0 \text{ and } \Delta T_{\text{surrounding}} > 0. \\ -\frac{A_{\text{radiating}} h_{\text{coefficient}} \Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}}{m_{\text{water}} h_{\text{latent}}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

2.4 Propagation

The propulsion mechanisms presented in this section are based on a piston-like expansion with a sufficiently large displacement and force during the movement.

2.4.1 Snail inspired propulsion

A snail moves by repeatedly contracting and expanding at the same time as it uses mucus to regulate the contact forces with the ground [18]. A simplified description of this propulsion is that the snail expands and contracts but is able to vary the frictional force depending on the direction of the contraction and expansion. Using non isotropic friction, a propulsion model is proposed in figure 4. A material with initial length l_1 expands, exerting an equal force on two boxes and it is assumed that the static friction is overcome for both boxes. Then the dynamic friction coefficient is assumed to vary depending on the direction of movement, resulting in a net force in the direction of lowest friction due to the leading box experiencing less friction. When the material contracts, the leading box instead experiences a greater frictional force, limiting the distance it moves back, whereas the lagging box more easily moves forwards. The net effect of this cycle is that the device as a whole moves.

Finding suitable materials with anisotropic frictional properties is hard in practice. In the spirit of the problem statement, the device should preferably work on a wide range of surfaces and in any direction. A relevant material is skins used in cross country skis. These uses small bristles aligned such that they resist movement in one direction (grip) and get aligned with the movement in the other direction (slide). A study by Frühwirth, Lehner and Wilfing (2018) [19] investigated the grip and slide friction coefficients of commercial cross country ski skins and found a maximum difference of $\mu_{\text{grip}} - \mu_{\text{slide}} \approx 2.3$.

Although this mechanism is shown to be able to create propulsion, it is limited by the length of thermal expansion. Even though thermal expansion potentially can perform a great amount of work, this mechanism is unable to utilize that force.

2.5 Car propulsion

Anecdotaly, propulsion using wheels is an efficient propulsion mechanism if the surface beneath is sufficiently even. In section 2.1 the discussed thermal expansion engines all produces linear motion, which would have to be converted to rotational motion to drive a pair of wheels. This is similar to how linear motion from pistons in a car engine has to be converted to rotational motion to drive a pair of wheels [20]. It is therefore reasonable to take inspiration from a car to construct a propulsion system. For the purposes of this report a car powertrain work through the following steps:

1. A combustion process produces linear motion
2. The linear motion is converted to rotational motion by a crankshaft

Figure 4: Schematic description of snail-like propulsion mechanism. Non-dotted lines represent frictional force when moving in direction indicated by expansion and the frictional forces satisfies $F_{\text{moving right}} < F_{\text{moving left}}$. 1) The force from the expansion is the same on both boxes, although the left box experiences a greater frictional force, resulting in the right box moving further. 2) Final state of expansion. The contraction force is the same on both boxes, although the right box experiences a greater frictional force due to the non isotropic friction, making the left box move further to the right. 3) After a completed cycle the entire device has been displaced to the right.

3. The rotational speed is decrease and torque is increased using gears
4. The final rotation is connected to the wheels

In this report, step 1 has been referred to as the *engine* and steps 2 – 4 will collectively be called a *drivetrain*.

A car engine operates much faster than the engine used in this study. This limits components that utilizes inertia, such as flywheels. The torque varies throughout a rotation of the crankshaft and is zero at when the piston is fully extended or contracted. A redesigned crankshaft would ideally supply a constant torque throughout a rotation. Designing a drive train that successfully deals with these challenges will be a focus of this report.

3 Method

The methodology was split into two parts. First the entire car was designed and then its performance was tested.

3.1 Design process

The design process was characterized by many iterations of the chosen design with the end goal to get a working prototype as quickly as possible. This dictated the choice of materials and mechanisms. For the piston mechanism a oral syringe⁴ was used because of its availability and

⁴Indeed, Swedish regulations on syringes makes it very hard to procure any other type of syringe <https://www.lakemedelsverket.se/sv/handel-med-lakemedel/sprutor-och-kanyler>.

comparatively good seal, stopping air from entering the syringe. LEGO® Technic™ was used as the basis for gears due to it being readily available, comparatively low friction and versatile to quickly test different gear setups.

The final design of the device was reached by iteratively making changes to the connection between the syringe piston and drivetrain as well as changing the mechanisms used in the crankshaft. After each redesign the prototype was put in a freezer to observe if the design was able to move the whole mechanism.

3.2 Measuring performance parameters

The syringe was put in a commercial freezer whose temperature was assumed to be $\Delta T_{\text{surrounding}} = -18^\circ\text{C}$ [21]. The volume of water inside the syringe was measured every 10 min and was initially, when all water was liquid, 5 mL. Based on equation (1) and measuring the freezing time t_{freeze} with constant $\Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}$ from the beginning of the expansion until the end of expansion, the heat transfer coefficient was estimated by equation (4),

$$h_{\text{coefficient}} = \frac{h_{\text{latent}} m_{\text{water}}}{A_{\text{radiating}} t_{\text{freeze}} \Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}}. \quad (4)$$

The rolling resistance of the final design was measured by connecting the device to a pulley with a mass hanging from it. The mass was increased using 1 g washers until the car started moving. The resulting gravitational force was then normalized by the weight of the device to get the rolling resistance coefficient.

3.3 Test of propagation and extrapolations

The propagation of the final device was tested using a freezing spray to freeze the water in the syringe that initially was at room temperature and filming the entire process. Liquid coolant was sprayed on the syringe, evaporating and cooling the water. It was sprayed perpendicular to the direction of movement to ensure that the freezing mechanism itself was the source of the propagation. When all water was frozen the ice was melted with a heat gun to confirm that the device would be able to reset itself without moving backwards. The total time to freeze all water with the cooling spray was 10 min and the melting process took an additional 10 min. The total displacement after a full cycle was measured.

Using the measures of used syringe and calculated values for heat transfer, trapezoidal integration of weather data [2] of equation (3) was performed to approximate the final device performance in realistic scenarios. All used values for variables in equations (1) to (3) are noted in table 1.

4 Results

In this section, the final design of the car is shown and the key mechanisms described. Parameters measured on the final device are used to extrapolate the results based on historical weather data.

4.1 Heat transfer coefficient

The heat transfer coefficient was estimated to $(15.3 \pm 10.4) \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}$ using equation (4) and error estimate using Taylor expansion with the uncertainty $\Delta t_{\text{freeze}} = \pm 5 \text{ min}$ being the greatest source of error. Engineers Edge [22] lists $h_{\text{coefficient}} = 15 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K} - 70 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}$ as a typical range for the heat transfer coefficient of liquid in a tubing with gas at atmospheric pressure surrounding it. The expansion in figure 5 shows the freezing process. Initially the liquid and plastic in the syringe is cooled down from room temperature to 0°C before any measurable expansion starts. The final expansion of 9% is also in agreement with [23]. The Pearson correlation coefficient

Table 1: Values used in extrapolation of results using equation (3). Note that $C_{P,\text{ice}}$ and $C_{P,\text{water}}$ were neglected by setting $T_{\text{low}} = T_{\text{high}} = T_{\text{formation}}$ in equation (1). This is motivated since they are two orders of magnitude smaller than h_{latent} .

Parameter	Used value
$A_{\text{radiating}}$	$2.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$
$h_{\text{coefficient}}$	$15.3 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$
$d_{\text{expansion}}$	$4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$
m_{water}	$4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}$
$C_{P,\text{ice}}$	$2.1 \times 10^3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
h_{latent}	$3.3 \times 10^5 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$
$C_{P,\text{water}}$	$4.2 \times 10^3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
A_{piston}	$9.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2$
$T_{\text{formation}}$	0°C
T_{low}	0°C
T_{high}	0°C
F_{load}	0 N
$\Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}$	From SMHI [2]

between the expansion and time is $\rho_{\text{pearson}} = 0.991$ which is agreement with the linear relation predicted by equation (3).

Figure 5: Syringe filled with 5 mL of water put inside a commercial freezer at -18°C . Resulting heat transfer coefficient from equation (4) was $(15.3 \pm 10.4) \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}$

4.2 Final design

A syringe was filled with 5 mL of water and shaken repeatedly to remove air bubbles. Then the tip of the syringe was sealed by melting the tip and then applying a thick layer of glue around the tip⁵. After this process 4 mL of water was left in the syringe.

The top of a syringe was connected to a lever with a mechanical advantage of 1 : 4, as shown in figure 6, using the force of the expansion to increase the total movement. This lever is connected to a gear with two additional levers, translating the linear motion to rotational, forming a crankshaft with roughly constant torque throughout the cycle.

⁵This step is crucial since even a small leakage at the tip will ruin the contraction.

Figure 6: Crankshaft mechanism designed to supply a roughly constant torque during expansion and contraction. The gray circles are fixed and the levers rotate around them. The white circles move along with the arms. The extended state of the system is shown with decreased opacity.

The rotation of the gear in figure 6 rotates both clockwise and counterclockwise, but the final vehicle should only move in one direction. The used design was inspired by [24] and is shown in figure 7. The core idea is to physically move the gears depending on the movement direction. Unfortunately to improve reliability and avoid the gears getting stuck, the lower right wheel in the design had to be removed in the final design, effectively creating rotation during the clockwise rotation and not transferring any rotation during counterclockwise rotation. The fully extended and contracted states of the final assembly are shown in figure 8, where the movement of the the crankshaft is clearly seen. A comparison of key specifications of the device and a normal passenger car are shown in table 2.

Figure 7: Mechanism used to convert both clockwise and counterclockwise rotation of the green gear to clockwise rotation of the yellow wheel.

4.3 Car movement

The observation of the freezing process was that the mechanism moved during short burst with some time in between them. Such a burst is shown in figure 9 where the device traveled 5.4 mm in 0.165 s. The total distance travelled by the device during a full cycle was 2.1 cm. The system was able to contract back to its initial state upon melting as shown in figure 8a.

Table 2: Comparison between "Thermal Snail" design in this study compared to a commercial car. Specification of Volkswagen Golf 2014 is, unless specified, from [25].

Car	Thermal Snail	Volkswagen Golf 2014
Engine displacement	4 mL	2 L
Cylinders	1	4
Smallest Gear Ratio	1:5	1:0.4 ⁶
Rolling resistance	(0.08 ± 0.01)	0.007 [26]
Curb weight	144 g	1394 kg
Dimensions	20 cm × 14 cm × 11 cm	4.2 m × 1.8 m × 1.5 m

(a) Contracted / liquid state

(b) Extended / frozen state

Figure 8: The two states of the final design of the thermal snail. The contracted state is after the car had gone through one freeze-melt cycle.

Figure 9: The device during movement. Here it moves 5.4 mm during 1.65 s, resulting in a velocity of 0.1 km h^{-1} .

4.4 Extrapolations with simplified model

The extrapolated performance of the device, as well as the performance of an ideal device, which would perform a full contraction or expansion every time the temperature changed from plus to minus degrees, are shown in table 3. Although naturally this is limited by the hourly resolution of the used dataset. Further, for each weather station, a day with the maximal observed number of cycles is shown in figure 10. This was 1.5 cycles for all stations. With the 2.1 cm propagation per cycle that the built device can perform, the expected distance traveled per year is $(90.7 \pm 23.3) \text{ cm}$.

Figure 10: Integration of the change of $r_{\text{ice/water}}$ from equation (3) at the most ideal days in the dataset for each station. N.b. that $1 - r_{\text{ice/water}}$ is shown in red in the plots.

Table 3: Model in equation (1) with values from table 1 calculated with temperature data between 1990 and 2020 from SMHI [2]. For $h_{\text{coefficient}} = \infty$ all water was assumed to change phase instantly when the temperature went from minus degrees to plus degrees. A cycle refers to the equivalent full expansion and contraction of the syringe, i.e. two cycles of a 50% expansion and subsequent 50% contraction would also be considered as one cycle. When applicable, the values were averaged over the 30 year time period with the standard deviation being shown.

Parameter	$h_{\text{coefficient}}$	Göteborg A	Krångede A	Nikkaluokta A
Latitude		57.72°	63.15°	67.85°
Yearly cycles	15.3	(22.4 ± 7.5)	(43.2 ± 11.1)	(39.8 ± 7.2)
Yearly cycles	∞	(64.0 ± 17.3)	(129.5 ± 21.3)	(127.2 ± 19.1)
Daily max cycles	15.3	1.5	1.5	1.5
Daily max cycles	∞	5	5.5	7
Yearly days with ≥ 3 cycles	∞	(0.6 ± 0.6) days	(1.5 ± 1.2) days	(2.1 ± 1.0) days

5 Discussion

This section discusses the limitations of the manufacturing process and implications of how the historical weather data can be used to improve the design.

5.1 Limitations in engine

The thermodynamic efficiency of the system is low due to the high latent heat of water compared to the mechanical work done by the system. If the energy required to change the temperature of the water is neglected, the thermal efficiency of the system is approximated as $d_{\text{expansion}} F_{\text{load}} / (m_{\text{water}} h_{\text{latent}})$. Although the efficiency can be significantly increased by having a gearbox that could utilize a greater F_{load} , this would lead to practical problems with the currently used materials. The efficiency could also be increased by using a smaller mass of water, which could be accomplished by using a thinner syringe.

The engine shape can be varied to significantly increase performance. In equation (3) it is clear that increasing $A_{\text{radiating}}$ and $h_{\text{coefficient}}$ would decrease the time for the phase transition. From table 3 it is clear that the amount of cycles in a year can be up to three times greater if the cooling rate were much higher. In order to change phase in less than an hour at the lowest recorded temperature in the SMHI data, $|\Delta T_{\text{surrounding}}| = 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, the product $A_{\text{radiating}} h_{\text{coefficient}}$ would have to be increase by a factor of 120 compared to the current value, without changing the total amount of water in the system. A radiator like system, where the surface area is maximized would aid in this. The material of the pipe could also be changed to something with a greater thermal conductivity than the currently used plastic, although it would most likely not amount to full 120 times increase. Furthermore thinner parts have a comparatively greater surface area, making them freeze quicker, which could potentially clog the system and prevent the piston from expanding as intended. This could be prevented by carefully insulating areas that needs to be frozen last, effectively designing to have a direction of the freezing. In that case a larger reservoir could be funneled into a thinner tube section, resulting in a much greater $d_{\text{expansion}}$ compared to the initial length of a reservoir. This creates a more compact system that better utilize the 10 cm maximum dimension. The design is inspired by a normal mercury thermometer [27] and is shown in figure 11.

Figure 11: A proposal for a thermal engine where the linear dimension of expansion can expand significantly compared to its initial width. To avoid clogging, parts of the engine are partially insulated to allow other areas to freeze earlier.

The funneling in figure 11 would also be applicable if the thermal expansion used a linear thermal expansion of a liquid instead of a phase change, although the isolation would not be necessary. The increased $d_{\text{expansion}}$ for a fixed linear dimension is useful since in practice it is hard to take advantage of small movements and decrease the gear ratio too much. Using a hydraulic system like this would not be possible with a compressible gas, which is an advantage compared to the methods proposed by Xiao et al. [8].

The system also naturally generates movement during the shrinking process, whereas the design by Xiao et al. used a constant force spring that was loaded during the expansion and used to aid the compression. Although the design used in this study was not able to drive the wheels during the shrinking, mostly due to friction in the conversion of rotation direction in figure 7. It was however able to move the rest of the crankshaft which shows that it is able to perform work.

Hysteresis is a major problem with the final design. If a small amount of air leaks into the syringe at some point during the heat-melt cycles, the ice is able to expand by compressing the air instead of pushing the piston. During the shrinking process, the air pressure decreases instead of moving the syringe back. This was often observed during the design iterations, but not in the final design, however it is likely that after enough freeze-melt cycle it will also be affected.

5.2 Limitations in drivetrain

The drivetrain is a significant problem with the final design. Due to the flexibility of structural elements in the design, it is unable to handle lower gear ratios since some elements of the design bends. The gears also has a tendency to get stuck. This problem is especially pronounced when changing the rotation direction through the mechanism in figure 7, where the alignment of the top rotating arm to the wheels are necessary. Moreover, the tilting process required to go between figure 7a and figure 7b does not result in any momentum towards the wheels. I.e. the thermal expansion is first used to tilt the mechanism before the gears will transfer any momentum to the wheels. Therefore decreasing the required amount of tilt would increase the performance.

6 Conclusions

This study has investigated how thermal expansion can be used to move a small device. An investigation of the Swedish climate and literature review of systems that are driven by thermal expansion concluded that the phase transition of water to ice was the expansion mechanism most suitable for Swedish climate. Due to the large forces involved in the expansion, the expansion was integrated into a mechanism inspired by a car powertrain. The final design was able to move 2.1 cm in a single freeze-melt-cycle. Compared to other mechanisms found in literature, the design is more suitable to scale down to a fixed linear dimension. A comparatively primitive manufacturing process dictated many design decisions. A more thorough manufacturing together

with other suggestions presented in the end of the report would potentially be able to increase the distance traveled by an order of magnitude in a given year.

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